

Implementation of socio-demographic attributes into SPENSER, a synthetic population tool

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Summary

A synthetic population is the representation of actual or future population when data about every individual is not available. It contains each individual's characteristics (e.g., age, sex) that are obtained from census and survey datasets. Currently, some tools allow generating synthetic populations for research in diverse fields but the number of attributes given is scarce. In this paper, we present an extension of the SPENSER tool that provides an increase number of attributes for each individual. Attributes such as marital status, children dependency, driving licence ownership, economic activity and occupation are obtained based on Census, UK Government and ONS datasets.

KEYWORDS: Synthetic population, simulation, socio demographics, attributes.

1. Introduction

Synthetic population generation is the procedure used to create a realistic representation of the actual or future population when individual records of all relevant members of the real group are not available (Borysov, et. al, 2019), (Miranda, 2020), (Moeckel, et. al, 2003). This representation is made considering attributes that define each individual's characteristic (e.g., sex, age, ethnicity, location), which can be obtained from sources such as census and surveys. The location and the composition of the population dictates current needs and demands, while projected changes in the population will dictate future needs (Lomax et al, Under Review).

SPENSER (Cruz Garcia, et.al, 2019) is a synthetic population tool that provides some socio-demographic characteristics of people in the UK, using Census 2011 data and projecting them up to 2030. SPENSER provides information about the sex, age, ethnic group, household ID and location (MSOA level) for each individual, and some other attributes related to the household where they are assigned (data only related to the household reference person). Sometimes, these attributes are not enough to identify more specific patterns in the society or to simulate realistic scenarios in mobility, ageing, equity, urban growth and other applications. In this paper, we present an extension of the SPENSER tool developing more attributes for each individual. Attributes such as marital status, children dependency, ownership of driving licence, economic activity and occupation are obtained based on Census, UK Government and ONS datasets.

This paper will describe the methodology developed to obtain the attributes (Section 2), the results obtained in a specific case-scenario (Section 3), future steps (Section 4) and conclusions (Section 5).

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2. Methodology

The implementation of attributes in a synthetic population is a relevant task because they provide a better representation of the real society and better decisions can be made to improve their quality of life. Smaller groups of the society could be visible and considered, addressing issues such as equity, household composition, social coherency and aging (Borysov, et. al, 2019). Some interesting attributes that can be included into a synthetic population are the marital status, the children dependency, the ownership of driving licence, the economic activity and occupation. These attributes were defined for each individual based on the following datasets (Python codes available in the GitHub repository https://github.com/DACNC/synthetic_population):

1. Marital status: This attribute classifies each individual in “Married”, “Couple” or “Single”, based on their age and the characteristics of the people they live with (**Figure 1**). Each status can define different behaviours and actions that a person can do depending on their daily responsibilities with their family (e.g., number of trips per day, task distribution between the members of the family).

Figure 1 Marital status. Dependencies (blue boxes) and types of marital status (grey boxes).

2. Children dependency: This attribute records whether individuals have children. People have different behaviours and needs depending if there are children in the household (e.g., escort them to school, more restrictive schedules and obligations, the need of living close to a school). This category is a Boolean value and depends on the age, members of the household, marital status and the presence of individuals under 18 years old in the household (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2 Children dependency. Dependencies (blue boxes) and types of children dependency (grey boxes).

- Driving licence: This category identifies those individuals with the ability to drive, based on their age, sex, number of cars in the household and information provided by the National Travel Survey (NTS) (National Travel Survey, 2021) (**Figure 3**). Owning a driving license provides more freedom to individuals in their decisions on where to live and how to move, among others.

Figure 3 Driving licence. Dependencies (blue boxes) and types of driving licence (grey boxes).

- Economic activity: This category classifies individuals in “Employed” (people working), “Unemployed” (people looking actively for a job) and “Inactive” (people that do not work and do not look for a job). It was assigned based on the age and sex, using data from Census 2011 (UK Office for National Statistics Census, 2011a) and projected to the year the synthetic population is developed using the Regional labour market statistics (ONS, 2020) (**Figure 4**). It allows identifying different types of routines and needs for each person (e.g., starting time of routines, identification of locations where they go).

Figure 4 Economic activity. Dependencies (blue boxes) and types of economic activity (grey boxes).

- Occupation: this category classifies individuals (employed and unemployed) in nine professional categories (**Figure 5**), which were assigned based on their age and sex, using data from Census 2011 (UK Office for National Statistics Census, 2011b) and the annual population survey-workplace analysis (UK Office for National Statistics Census, 2011c). The knowledge of this attribute allows the identification and estimation of additional attributes, such as income and life style (e.g. types and number of daily routines) for each individual.

Figure 5 Occupation. Dependencies (blue boxes) and types of occupation (grey boxes).

3. Results

These socio-demographic attributes were calculated based on outputs from the SPENSER tool in a case-scenario of the North-East of England for the year 2019. Obtained results were compared and validated against UK Government, ONS and NTS datasets, with the following observations:

The number of individuals with a specific marital status and children dependency were based on data obtained directly from the SPENSER tool and no further validation is required.

Driving licences were assigned to population aged 17 and over and differences between groups of age and by gender were up to 3.92% and 1.47% respectively, when compared against NTS data (**Tables 1 and 2**).

Table 1 Percentage of people with driving licence per sex.

	Result	NTS table NTS9901	Difference
% Population > 17	71.59	70.84	0.75
% Males > 17	80.47	79.00	1.47
% Females > 17	63.21	63.32	-0.11

Table 2 Percentage of people with driving licence per sex and group of age.

	17 - 20	21 - 29	30 - 39	40 - 49	50 - 59	60 - 69	70+
% males driving	33.99	64.99	82.99	88.99	88.99	88.99	80.99
NTS Table NTS0201	33.90	64.51	82.64	88.99	89.22	90.39	81.32
Difference	0.09	0.48	0.35	0.00	-0.23	-1.40	-0.33
% females driving	30.99	53.99	65.99	73.99	73.99	73.99	49.14
NTS Table NTS0201	31.34	53.61	66.08	73.62	73.77	70.07	49.08
Difference	-0.35	0.38	-0.09	0.37	0.22	3.92	0.06

Economic activity results were within 1% to those obtained from the Regional labour market statistics (ONS, 2020), except for unemployed males older than 64, where differences between employed and

inactive made this value be 0.48% bigger than expected but tolerated. **Table 3** shows the results obtained of employed, unemployed and inactive people for each gender and range of age.

Table 3 Percentage of employed, unemployed and inactive people, per sex and range of age.

	% Employed per range of age				
	16 - 24	25 - 34	35 - 49	50 - 64	65+
Males result	50.32	83.56	87.25	68.54	9.23
Regional labour market statistics: HI01 Headline indicators for the North East 2b 2019 (males)	51.85	84.18	87.79	68.80	9.61
Difference	-0.73	-0.62	-0.54	-0.27	-0.38
Females result	47.65	73.49	78.19	65.26	4.54
Regional labour market statistics: HI01 Headline indicators for the North East 2c 2019 (females)	48.65	73.05	77.93	66.22	5.13
Difference	-1.00	0.44	0.26	-0.96	-0.59
	% Unemployed per range of age				
	16 - 24	25 - 34	35 - 49	50 - 64	65+
Males result	15.84	6.49	3.43	6.88	2.50
Regional labour market statistics: HI01 Headline indicators for the North East 2b 2019 (males)	15.97	6.44	3.45	5.95	1.03
Difference	-0.13	0.05	-0.02	0.93	1.48
Females result	13.04	4.48	3.75	3.49	N/A
Regional labour market statistics: HI01 Headline indicators for the North East 2c 2019 (females)	12.28	5.06	3.45	3.21	No data
Difference	0.77	-0.58	0.30	0.28	N/A
	% Inactive per range of age				
	16 - 24	25 - 34	35 - 49	50 - 64	65+
Males result	39.26	10.63	9.65	26.40	90.53
Regional labour market statistics: HI01 Headline indicators for the North East 2b 2019 (males)	38.29	10.02	9.08	26.84	90.29
Difference	0.97	0.62	0.57	-0.44	0.24
Females result	45.21	23.06	18.76	32.37	95.02
Regional labour market statistics: HI01 Headline indicators for the North East 2c 2019 (females)	44.54	23.05	19.29	31.58	94.80
Difference	0.67	0.01	-0.53	0.79	0.22

Occupations were assigned with a maximum difference of 3.49% against data from Annual population survey - workplace analysis dataset (**Table 4**).

Table 4 Percentage of occupations.

	% Result	% Annual population survey - workplace analysis (2019)	% Difference
Managers, Directors and Senior Officials	10.93	8.45	2.48
Professional Occupations	17.88	20.66	-2.78
Associate Prof & Tech Occupations	12.47	12.59	-0.12
Administrative and Secretarial Occupations	8.61	11.24	-2.63
Skilled Trades Occupations	11.78	8.29	3.49
Caring, Leisure and Other Service Occupations	10.97	11.55	-0.57
Sales and Customer Service Occupations	7.45	9.53	-2.08
Process, Plant and Machine Operatives	7.93	5.82	2.12
Elementary occupations	11.97	11.87	0.10

4. Future steps

The project will continue implementing additional socio-demographic attributes into the existing SPENSER tool. Currently, the attributes considered for inclusion are:

- Income: to identify the wealth of individuals and quality/style of life.
- Health: to identify the grade of general health (good, fair or bad).
- Bike ownership: to identify those individuals with the possibility to use the bike.
- Inactive: to identify the different categories of inactive people in the area (e.g. students, retired, looking after family/home and long time sick).

5. Conclusion

The current paper has explained how some socio-demographic attributes have been calculated based on outputs from the SPENSER tool in a case-scenario of the North-East of England for the year 2019. The obtained results show very small differences when compared against existing datasets from ONS, NTS and UK Government. The implementation of these attributes allow improved definition of the heterogeneity within the population and increased spatial detail. It can provide improved knowledge about how the population is distributed and the type of needs that can be satisfied.

This project will be used to develop a synthetic population of the North-East of England to analyse and simulate urban mobility policy scenarios in Newcastle upon Tyne and Gateshead with the aim of reducing the use of private cars and CO2 emissions.

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Biographies

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Alistair Ford is a Lecturer in Geospatial Data Analytics in the Geospatial Engineering group at Newcastle University. His research interests include spatial modelling of urban environments, simulating land-use and transport systems, and their interactions with environmental factors such as extreme weather events